

Part 11 Biomechanics in endodontics (Article Series), Importance of the ferrule when bond is partially lost, Stupid models for interpreting living organs

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Abstract

Modern restorations are highly dependent upon bonding. Nevertheless, mechanical retention is superior to the bonding as it provides implementation of the tooth structure itself. In this paper, we want to investigate the importance of the ferrule on the performance of the endodontically treated teeth.

Keywords: Ferrule, Bond, Endodontics, Fiber post, Metallic post, Stiffeners.

Introduction

Restoration of the endodontically treated teeth is a subject with multiple issues that need a segregated approach. In the case of restoration of endodontically treated teeth, the ferrule had a mechanical role. This role is supplemented with the aid of a bond at the base of the restoration. Loss of this bond is causing the restoration to depend on the remaining tooth mechanically or on the mechanical aids, such as the post. To what extent this dependence is important, we want to present the next model. We suggest a model of no bond at the base of the crown with just a bond to the ferrule or the post.

Methods

The models here are the same model as the numerical simulation of the ferrule, with the same boundary conditions and material properties. (1).

Figure 1 Ferruleless model with no bonding at the green region

We had introduced contact at the base of the restoration sub model, as represented by the green region in the Figure 1, where the crown model could be separated and compressed. In the previous model, they are behaving as a single continuous entity.

Results

In the next models, we selected the most important engineering criteria to investigate the effect of the ferrule. The difference between the bondless and bonded models, both with a ferrule, had not been explored.

Even the ferrule should be evaluated parametrically, both numerically and physically, in terms of dimensions. (2).

Figure 2 If the base of the crown had lost the adhesion to the tooth, the pressure would be higher in the case of a ferruleless model.

Figure 3 The gap will be essentially larger.

The extent to which the pressure will affect the surfaces needs more investigation. Loss of contact will exaggerate the mechanical loads, and poorer results will ensue.

Figure 4 The strain between 2 models is totally different. The model on the left is the ferruled model.

We should always remember that the tooth is a fibrous-based structure with complex orthotropicity (3). The presence of the ferrule makes the tooth behave like it had been crowned, which provide unparallel secure to the horizontal forces or the horizontal component of the oblique forces. We could regard the model with a ferrule as a tooth with a short crown.

Figure 5 Concentration of the strain energy density on a single side with a disturbed distribution in the case of the ferruleless model. This result makes the furred model in favor.

Figure 6 The strain energy is not reaching to the edge of the model, providing excellent protection.

The deeper transfer of the stresses is an essential prerequisite for the endodontic treatment.

The most coronal part of the root should be bypassed to the deeper portions and should be preserved from deformation.

Figure 7 The ferruled model is on the left.

We should always remember the circular pattern of the collagen fibers' orientation in the dentine architecture. The evaluation of the endodontically treated teeth depends on multiple factors, not just a single factor. All the

final comparisons are of the soft post with respect to the current trend of implementing it, although we encourage the restorative dentist to select the other variation.

References

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024, he was involved in many research projects in biomechanics and biomechatronics. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth, and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties, as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as a maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, the largest secondary referral center in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.